

over which it has to operate. Also, $-O^-$ of the phenoxide ion is more roomier here than in 3MeOHB due to the distant position of the methyl group in 4MeOHB, so the stability of the phenoxide ion is relatively increased in 4MeOHB. Thus 4MeOHB is found to be stronger acid than 3MeOHB. What has been seen for 4MeOHB is also true for 5MeOHB. Therefore, 5MeOHB has an acid strength very close to that of 4MeOHB, or, it should be slightly stronger acid since the inductive effect would be expected to be even smaller. The data (Table 1) obtained support this prediction.

By substituting an oxime group for a keto oxygen and comparing their pK values (Tables 1), it was found that ketoximes are more acidic than the corresponding ketones. The substituting of a methyl group reduces the acidity of the parent ketoximes due to steric effect on the 'H-bond' between the phenolic 'OH' and 'N' of the oxime.

TABLE I. PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS:
MEDIUM: 75% DIOXANE—25% WATER (BY VOLUME)

Reagent	$\log PK^H$
2-OH-butyrophenone (OHB)	12.39
2-OH-3-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (3MeOHB)	13.24
2-OH-4-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (4MeOHB)	12.70
2-OH-5-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (5MeOHB)	12.67
2-OH-butyrophenoneoxime (OHBO)	11.81
2-OH-3-CH ₃ -butyrophenoneoxime (3MeOHBO)	12.16
2-OH-5-CH ₃ -butyrophenoneoxime (5MeOHBO)	11.90

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Further studies on Flemichapparin-A, a new chromenochalcone isolated from *Flemingia chappar**

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BASED on spectral evidence (UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectra), the structure of flemichapparin-A, a new chromenochalcone occurring in the whole plant of *Flemingia chappar* was first proposed as (I)¹.

* This work was presented at the 'Convention of Chemists' held at Allahabad University, Allahabad, October 8-12, 1972.

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At a later date, Merlini *et al* arrived at the same structure (I) for a new chromenochalcone², m.p. 191°-92°, isolated from the leaves or flowers of *F. chappar*². The properties of the latter agree with those of flemichapparin-A. We now furnish further independent chemical and spectral evidence in favour of the structure (I) for flemichapparin-A.

Catalytic hydrogenation of (I) with Adam's catalyst in alcohol furnished the corresponding tetrahydro-derivative, C₂₀H₂₂O₄ (M⁺ 326), m.p. 91°-92°, proving the presence of two easily reducible double bonds. The mass spectral data of the latter [m/e 326 (M⁺) 270, 221, 165 and 91] speak in favour of a chroman ring and two -OH groups in ring A. Thus, the chroman ring suffers the expected retro-Diels-Alder cleavage giving rise to a prominent peak at m/e 270 (M⁺-56; M⁺-CH₃C=CH₂). The occurrence

of the peaks at m/e 221 (M⁺ - 105; M⁺ - C₆H₅CH₂CH₂), m/e 165 (m/e 270 - C₆H₅CH₂CH₂) and m/e 91 (tropolium ion) proves that a dihydrocinnamoyl residue is present in tetrahydroflemichapparin-A. Ozonolysis of flemichapparin-A (I) furnished benzaldehyde as one of its reaction products thereby proving the unsubstituted nature of ring B.

The integrated 60 MHz NMR spectrum (Table 1) has also been found to be in excellent agreement with the structure (II) for tetrahydroflemichapparin-A. A sharp 1H-singlet at 7.11δ provides further evidence that it must be due to the C-6 proton as has been observed in the case of hexahydroflemingin-B (III)³ and hexahydroflemingin-C (IV)³ having similar 2,4,5-substitution pattern and identical attachment of the chroman ring. The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 240 (log ε 3.66) 290 (log ε 4.17) and 350 nm (log ε 3.83)] of (II) also resembles that of hexahydroflemingin-B (III) and hexahydroflemingin-C (IV) thereby adding further corroborative evidence regarding the correctness of structure (II).

* Prof. Merlini (Milan) has agreed to retain the name flemichapparin-A first proposed by us (personal communication).

TABLE 1*

Chemical shift δ	No. of protons	Splitting pattern	Assignment of protons
1.38	6	<i>s</i>	2- <i>ter</i> .CH ₃
1.83	2	<i>t</i> (<i>J</i> = 6 Hz)	-CH ₂ (Chroman)
2.71	2	<i>t</i>	-CH ₂ (Chroman)
3.11	4	<i>s</i> (broad)	-C-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -aryl O
5.16	1	<i>s</i>	C ₅ -OH (disappears on D ₂ O exchange).
7.11	1	<i>s</i>	aromatic (C ₆ -H)
7.25	5	<i>s</i>	aromatic (B ring)
13.83	1	<i>s</i>	C ₂ -OH (disappears on D ₂ O exchange).

* Taken in CDCl₃ with TMS as internal standard. Signals are denoted in the usual way: *s* = singlet; *t* = triplet.

1

V

Flemichapparin-A (I), on boiling with acetic acid or aqueous NaOH for 6 hr. in N₂ atmosphere, afforded an isomeric product, C₂₀H₁₈O₄, m.p. 161°-162°, in poor yield (10-15%). The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 256 (log ϵ 4.33), 310 (log ϵ 3.66) and 350 nm (log ϵ 3.66)] is compatible with a flavanone structure (V) as the latter exhibits triple maxima (with bathochromic shifts of the maxima) very similar to the UV spectra of 6:7:3':4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone⁴ and 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy-flavanone⁵. The 60 MHz NMR spectrum (in CDCl₃) also suggests a flavanone structure (V) for this transformation product. The chromene ring is defined by the appearance of two olefinic protons at δ 6.6 and δ 5.56 δ , each appearing as a doublet (*J* = 10Hz) and two *ter*. methyls at 1.5 δ as a 6H-singlet. The aromatic protons (B ring) signal around 7.43 as a multiplet and the phenolic -OH as a singlet at 5.26 (disappears on D₂O exchange). The C-5 proton appears as a singlet at 7.30 δ . The occurrence of a rough triplet around 2.93 δ and an unresolved quartet around 5.50 δ suggests that these

signals are most probably due to the C-3 and C-2 protons^{5,6} of the flavanone derivative (V). Further studies on the chemistry of (I) are underway.

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Application of Viscosity Equations for the System : Barium Soap-Water and Propanol-1

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IN the previous communications^{1,2} the viscosity of barium soaps (valerate and caproate) solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions has been studied. In the present work, an attempt has been made to apply the various viscosity equations^{4,5} for the above system with a view to find out the nature of micelles formed in soap solutions in mixed solvents.

Experimental

The preparation of the soaps and measurements of the viscosity has been described in the previous communications^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Several equations³⁻⁵ have been put forward for testing the viscosity of electrolytes and non-electrolytes solutions⁶. However, the viscosity of Barium soap solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions has been satisfactorily represented in the wide range of concentrations by equations:

$$\text{Vand} : \frac{1}{C} = \frac{(0.921)^{-1}}{V} \frac{1}{\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}} + Q\bar{V} \quad \dots (1)$$

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